

ISic0011

I.Sicily inscription 0011

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

limestone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Panhormus

Place of origin (modern)

Palermo

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Imp(eratori)] · Caes(ari) · M(arco)
2. [A]urelio · Anto
3. [n]ino · Aug(usto) · divi
4. [A]ntonini · f(ilio) · divi · Hadri[ani]
5. [n]ep(oti) · divi · Traiani · Parth(ici)
6. [pr]onepoti · divi · Nervae
7. [a]bnep(oti) · pont(ifici) · max(imo) · trib(unicia) · p(otestate) · XVII
8. [c]o(n)s(uli) · III · r(es) · p(ublica) · Panhormit(anorum)

Apparatus

Text of ILMusPalermo

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491772

EDR 137644
EDCS 22000856

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. *Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum*. Berlin. At 10.7270 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650787>)

Bivona, L. 1970. Iscrizioni latine lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelia*. Palermo. At 11

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